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Figure S2. Calcium imaging in MFC and in non compartmentalized DRGs A) Scheme of the MFC Did' and Fluo-4 loading process with images of loaded cells merged with transmitted light. Scale bar= 100 μ m. B) Results of compartmentalized DRGs at DIV 6. Percentage of response to capsaicin and menthol, menthol and AITC or capsaicin and AITC normalized to KCl in DRGs cultured in MFC. $N=4$ animals, 2 males and 2 females; $n \geq 2$ coverslips per animal; total number of crossing neurons=747. C-E) Results of non-compartmentalized DRGs at DIV 6, cultured with soma compartment media. C) Quantification of the percentage of response to capsaicin and menthol, menthol and AITC or capsaicin and AITC normalized to KCl response. Data are represented as quantitative Venn Diagram. D) Quantification of the percentage of response to capsaicin, menthol or AITC normalized to KCl divided by sex. E) Quantification of the size of the response to capsaicin, menthol or AITC normalized to KCl response divided by sex. $N=4$ mice, 2 males and 2 females. $n \geq 2$ coverslips per animal. Total number of neurons= 5498.

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2 **Figure S3. Mouse DRGs co-cultured with human keratinocytes in microfluidic**
 3 **chambers** A) Schematic upper view of microfluidic chamber with neurons and keratinocytes
 4 B) Axonal side with keratinocytes fully confluent at DIV 6, when calcium imaging was
 5 performed. Scale bar = 100 μ m. C) MTT results on human keratinocytes (HaCaT). Statistical
 6 analysis Kruskal-Wallis test, Dunn's multiple comparisons test. N=3 independent
 7 experiments, each performed in triplicate. D) Percentage of response to capsaicin and
 8 menthol, menthol and AITC or capsaicin and AITC normalized to somal KCl response.

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2 **Figure S4. Effect of inflammatory mediators on axonal density.** (A and B) Representative
3 images of sensory neurons loaded with the calcein fluorescent dye in MFC. Axonal
4 compartment was treated with vehicle (H₂O) (A) or inflammatory mediators (B) on DIV5 for
5 24h, and the density of axonal ends was followed at 0 (DIV6) and 48h (DIV8) post-treatment.
6 (C) Axonal density was estimated by quantifying the mean fluorescence in the axonal
7 compartment on each day and normalized with respect to that existing pre-treatment (DIV5).
8 Values denote the mean ± SEM. n=4.

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3 **Figure S5. Effect of paclitaxel on axonal density.** (A and B) Representative images of
4 sensory neurons loaded with the calcein fluorescent dye in MFC. Axonal compartment was
5 treated with vehicle (DMSO 0.04%) (A) or paclitaxel 1 μ M (B) on DIV5 for 24h, and the
6 density of axonal ends was followed at 0 (DIV6), 48h (DIV8) and 96h (DIV10) post-treatment.
7 (C) Axonal density was estimated by quantifying the mean fluorescence in the axonal
8 compartment on each day and normalized with respect to that existing pre-treatment (DIV5).
9 Values denote the mean \pm SEM. $n=4$.

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1 **Table S1** Media composition for the DRGs-keratinocytes co-culture

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DIV	SOMA COMPARTMENT 200 µL/well		NERVE ENDINGS/KERATINOCYTES COMPARTMENT 100 µL/well	
DIV 0	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
DIV 1	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		DMEM GlutaMAX (Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco)	10%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	L-Glutamine (200 mM, Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	50 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	50 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL		
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL		
DIV 3 DIV 5	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		DMEM GlutaMAX (Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco)	10%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	L-Glutamine (200 mM, Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL		
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL		

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